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Transport impedance in a portable PEMFC working under passive conditions

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Abstract

Mass transport impedances, relating electrical and transport variables, are most useful to study kinetics of flow-based electrochemical systems like fuel cells. We have used the *Current-modulated Hydrogen-flow rate spectroscopy* (CH2S) to monitor mass transport in the anode of proton exchange membrane fuel cells (PEMFCs) by modulating current load, I , and measuring the perturbed hydrogen flow-rate, Q_{H_2} , ($H(j\omega) = nFAQ_{H_2}/I$). CH2S provides characteristic times of transport processes in the porous anode under working conditions (Fig.1), from which in-operando effective *diffusivity of hydrogen* can be obtained using the analytical model for transport in the gas-diffusion layer [1].

Figure 1. CH2S magnitude and angle for a passive and a conventional PEMFC.

In this communication, CH2S is applied to a PEMFC operated under passive conditions, i.e. fed with static hydrogen and air atmospheres. This operation mode is very convenient for small and portable applications because it avoids the use of convective elements for gases inlet, allowing a decrease in weight and volume of hydrogen power systems. However, the slow water removal from passive cells leads to high water saturation in the porous electrodes and, with it, to important transport losses. Consequently, passive cells attain typically lower power densities per unit active area compared with conventional PEMFCs. CH2S may help to identify and palliate such losses. Fig.1 compares CH2S results for passive and conventional PEMFCs, including experimental (dots) and theoretical curves (line). The transport difficulties in passive operation are characterized by lower CH2S magnitude and higher t_2 (lower H₂ diffusivity). The diffusivity of hydrogen will be analyzed under different experimental conditions in a passive PEMFC (p-PEMFC) including the active area size, and current density. The hydrogen diffusivity will be compared with that of a conventional, convective, cell.

Introduction

The *Current-modulated Hydrogen-flow rate Spectroscopy* (CH2S) is an impedance technique that relates the hydrogen flow rate, Q_{H_2} at the inlet of the anode of a proton exchange membrane fuel cell (PEMFC) with the current generated, I . The transfer function, $H(j\omega)$, obeys the following relation [1,2]:

$$H(j\omega) = nFA \frac{Q_{H_2}}{I}, \tag{1}$$

where n is the number of exchanged electrons in the reaction ($n=2$ for hydrogen oxidation), F ($=96485 \text{ C mol}^{-1}$) the Faraday constant, A the electrode area, ω the angular frequency, and j is the complex number. This transfer function has been calculated for transport in the gas diffusion layer (GDL) of the anode of a PEMFC, leading to [1]:

$$H(j\omega) = \text{sech} \left(L_{GDL} \sqrt{\frac{j\omega}{D_{H_2}}} \right), \tag{2}$$

where L_{GDL} is the gas diffusion layer (GDL) thickness and D_{H_2} is the effective hydrogen diffusivity. By applying Eq. 2 to the experimental CH2S curves it is possible to measure in-operando the hydrogen diffusivities in the GDL of PEMFC anodes. An expression including the possibility of reversible chemical kinetics within the GDL (adsorption/desorption, or possible reversible reactions of hydrogen) is also provided in Ref. [1].

The passive operation of a PEMFC consists of the feeding of the cell with quasi-static atmosphere, i.e. without applying convective forces for hydrogen and oxygen inlet in anode and cathode, respectively [3]. The passive PEMFC (p-PEMFC) does not have conventional flow-field plates, i.e. plates with channels in contact with the back surface of the electrode for the flow and distribution of gases, where elimination of the water produced is assisted by the convective flow. Instead, in a p-PEMFC, electrodes back surfaces are in contact with static atmospheres of the reactant gases, and water is eliminated by natural forces (evaporation, hydrophilic dragging, gravity). Fig. 1 compares schematically the conventional and the passive configurations. Most convenient for p-PEMFC configuration are an air-breathing cathode with back surface in contact with the ambient atmosphere, and a gas-tight dead-end anode containing a hydrogen atmosphere. Details of the passive PEMFC design used here have been provided in reference [4]. This operation mode is of technical interest for small and portable applications, because it allows a simplification of the fuel cell system.

Fig. 1. Schemes comparing the conventional with the passive feeding configurations of a PEMFC.

The performance of the p-PEMFC relies on natural forces for the elimination of liquid water from the electrodes. These forces are principally the diffusion through the porous electrodes, the evaporation of water from the electrode surface, and the dragging of drops over the electrode surface by forces like hydrophilic/hydrophobic interactions and gravity. Their effect depends on morphology and transport properties of the electrodes, having major impact at intermediate and high current densities, or after long operation times (see B1701 communication by us in this congress).

1. Scientific Approach

In this communication, the CH₂S technique is applied to the study of p-PEMFCs, in order to measure in-operando the diffusivity of hydrogen in the anode. In-operando hydrogen diffusivity in a p-PEMFC is compared with that in a conventional-convective PEMFC, and studied as a function of current density and active area size.

2. Experiments

p-PEMFCs with circular active area have been used with a design described in previous works [3]. The cathode is air-breathing, having commercial gas diffusion electrode (GDE) (FCSTORE, 0.30 mg Pt·cm⁻²; 30 wt% ionomer; 10 μm CL thickness; 300 μm woven carbon cloth GDL with MPL), and a Nafion 212 NR (Ion Power, Dupont). The back surface is in contact with a gold coated Ni grid (Dexmet). The cathode has a columnar plate [4] in order to maximize the contact with the ambient air and facilitate water elimination. The plate also maintains clamping pressure with the anodic plate to minimize electric resistances between membrane-electrode assembly components. The anode is the same commercial GDE, operated in full dead-end mode. Operation of the p-PEMFC is carried out under ambient conditions (23 °C and 30%RH), feeding the anode with a static pressure (0.8bar_g) of dry hydrogen in the dead-end, and the cathode with ambient air. The cell is self-heated attaining a temperature of 30 °C ± 5°C during CH₂S measurements.

CH₂S response of p-PEMFC is compared with a conventional single PEMFC having flow field plates (gold coated Stainless Steel 316, 3mm thickness) with double serpentine channeling, 1mm² cross section area each (1mm x 1mm, width x depth), disposed in cross-flow the anodic respect to the cathodic. The active area is 15.2cm², and same commercial electrodes and membrane are used as for the passive cell. For operation, the cell is fed with 100% humidified H₂/O₂, λ_{O₂}=3.0 and dead-end anode (technically λ_{H₂}=1.0), at 30°C and 1bar.

For CH₂S measurements, cell current is controlled with an electronic load (Kikusui PLZ164WA) while the hydrogen flow-rate entering the cell is measured with an electronic flow-meter (AWM3100V, Honeywell) placed before the anode inlet port. The output signal of the flow-meter is calibrated periodically by applying Faraday law to the current with dead-end anode. A sinusoidal current modulation of 50 mA peak-to-peak is superposed to the dc current load by means of the ac-generator of a commercial potentiostat/galvanostat (Autolab 30N, Metrohm). The Frequency Response Analyser of the same potentiostat is used to measure and calculate the transfer function, by connecting the flow-meter signal to the X port and the current load output signal to the Y port. More experimental details are in [5]. CH₂S was carried out in the frequency range from 1 kHz to 0.01 Hz, and the response analyzed with a commercial Origin software. The experimental set-up is shown in Fig. 2a, together with photographs of the conventional PEMFC (Fig. 2b) and p-PEMFC (Fig. 2c) used in this work.

Fig. 2. a) Experimental set-up for CH₂S measurements. b) Conventional-convective PEMFC single cell. c) Passive PEMFC (p-PEMFC).

3. Results

In this section, hydrogen transport properties in the anode of a p-PEMFC are compared with those of a conventional, convective cell using CH₂S (cf. Figs.2b and c). Then, the hydrogen diffusivities in the p-PEMFC are studied as a function of cell active area size and current density.

Comparing CH₂S responses of a p-PEMFC and a conventional PEMFC.- Figure 3 shows Bode plots of the CH₂S of a conventional and a passive cell.

Fig. 3. CH₂S of a p-PEMFC and a conventional PEMFC. The lines correspond to the fitting of results to Eqs. 2 and 3.

Three hydrogen mass transport signals explain the changes in the magnitude and angle of CH₂S [1]. For the analysis, a least-square fitting is carried out to the following expression:

$$H(j\omega) = \sum_i w_i H_i(j\omega), \tag{3}$$

Where H_i are the transfer functions (Eq. 2) and w_i the weight factors for each of the signals (i). Results of the fitting are given in Table I, where diffusivity and the thickness of the layer are merged in a single characteristic time k_i :

$$k_i = \frac{L_i^2}{D_i}. \tag{4}$$

The effective hydrogen diffusivities can be obtained from k_i using thicknesses measured from SEM cross sectional images for L_{GDL} ($= 250 \mu\text{m}$) and ($L_{MPL} = 50 \mu\text{m}$). The results are included in Table I.

Table I. Results of the fitting of the CH₂S results in Fig. 3 to the theory (Eqs. 2 and 3), for a passive and a convective (conventional) cell. Signals assignation and effective hydrogen diffusivities calculated from Eq. 4.

Passive PEMFC	Parameter	Value	Standard Error
Signal 1: Experimental set-up	w_1	0.813	0.008
	k_1, s	0.0038	10^{-4}
Signal 2: GDL	w_2	0.06	0.04
	k_2, s	1.3	0.9
	$D_{GDL}, \text{cm}^2\text{s}^{-1}$	$4.8 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$3 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Signal 3: MPL	w_3	0.13	0.03
	k_3, s	8	3
	$D_{MPL}, \text{cm}^2\text{s}^{-1}$	$0.03 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$0.01 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Convective PEMFC			
Signal 1: Experimental set-up	w_1	0.75	0.06
	k_1, s	0.0025	$3E-4$
Signal 2: GDL	w_2	0.19	0.06
	k_2, s	0.019	0.009
	$D_{GDL}, \text{cm}^2\text{s}^{-1}$	$330 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$160 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Signal 3: MPL	w_3	0.07	0.04
	k_3, s	5	4
	$D_{MPL}, \text{cm}^2\text{s}^{-1}$	$0.03 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$0.02 \cdot 10^{-4}$

The signal attributed to the experimental set-up time response, Signal 1, shows faster response for the convective cell ($k_1 = 0.0025\text{s}$) than the passive cell configuration ($k_1 = 0.0038\text{s}$). Although the high frequency limit available for CH₂S is mostly due to the flow-meter time response [5], the cell may have also some influence in this limit.

According to our assignation in previous works [1], signals 2 and 3 must be attributed to diffusivity in the anodic GDLs and MPLs, respectively. Being identical electrodes in both PEMFC configurations, the differences in time response are due to the cell operation mode. Hence, larger GDL time constant for the passive ($k_2 = 1.3\text{s}$) than for the conventional ($k_2 = 0.019\text{s}$) cell corresponds to a H₂ diffusivity 50 times lower. The difference must be due to the high saturation levels attained by the GDL in passive operation, because of the slow transport of water and its removal by passive forces (diffusion, evaporation) (A relation between the gas diffusivity of a GDL and its pores water saturation can be found in [6]). Signal 3, attributed to the MPL, shows however little change, being $k_3 = 8\text{s}$ for the passive operation and $k_3 = 5\text{s}$ for the convective operation, which implies lower effect of passive mode on the transport properties of this layer.

Active area size.- The size of the active area may influence the transport properties of p-PEMFCs due to possible exacerbation of lateral inhomogeneities in water transport. Fig. 4 shows CH₂S response of a cell with 7cm² active area compared with a cell with 12.6cm² area. The analysis of the three CH₂S signals are in Table II.

Fig. 4. CH₂S of two p-PEMFCs differing in the active area size.

Table II. Results of the fitting of the CH₂S in Fig. 4 to the theory (Eqs. 2 and 3), for two passive cells with different active area size.

Area: 12.6cm ²		Parameter	Value	Standard Error
Signal 1: Experimental set-up	w_1		0.828	0.007
	k_1, s		0.0038	1.E-4
Signal 2: GDL	w_2		0.07	0.03
	k_2, s		1.4	0.8
	D_{GDL}, cm^2s^{-1}		$4.4 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Signal 3: MPL	w_3		0.14	0.03
	k_3, s		9	3
	D_{MPL}, cm^2s^{-1}		$0.028 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$0.009 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Area: 7cm ²		Parameter	Value	Standard Error
Signal 1: Experimental set-up	w_1		0.855	0.004
	k_1, s		0.0034	4E-5
Signal 2: GDL	w_2		0.060	0.008
	k_2, s		0.35	0.08
	D_{GDL}, cm^2s^{-1}		$18 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$4.1 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Signal 3: MPL	w_3		0.103	0.009
	k_3, s		4.7	0.7
	D_{MPL}, cm^2s^{-1}		$0.053 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$0.008 \cdot 10^{-4}$

Results in Table II show that smaller areas allow faster response of the cell, as reflected by the smaller $k_1 = 0.0034s$ against $k_1 = 0.0038s$ for 7cm² and 12.6cm², respectively. Signals 2 and 3, related with the hydrogen transport in GDL and MPL of the anode, respectively, have also a significant dependence on cell size. In both signals, increasing active area size gives rise to a decrease in the diffusivities measured, which reflects larger transport difficulties for hydrogen. It is possible that larger active area of the passive cell favours water saturation towards the centre of the area, as observed with neutron radiography (see B1701 communication in this conference).

Current density. - Finally, the effect of current density on the transport properties of the anode of a p-PEMFC is analyzed with CH₂S. Fig. 5 shows CH₂S spectra at three current densities (active area 7cm²), and the analysis in Table III. As observed with conventional cells in a previous work [1], current density changes the diffusivities of GDL and MPL in different ways due to different nature of hydrogen transport in each case. While k_2 (GDL) remains almost unchanged with current density, for the values probed here, indicating little change in anodic GDL diffusivity, a decrease in k_3 time constant is observed with current reflecting the improvement of the MPL diffusivity. In previous work of CH₂S response in conventional cells, we concluded that current density activates MPL diffusivity [1].

Fig. 5. CH₂S signal of a passive PEMFC at three current densities.

Table III. Results of the fitting of the CH₂S in Fig. 5 to the theory (Eqs. 2 and 3), for a p-PEMFC cell run at different current densities.

$i=180 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$	Parameter	Value	Standard Error
Signal 1: Experimental set-up	w_1	0.877	0.005
	$k_1, \text{ s}$	0.0029	5.E-5
Signal 2: GDL	w_2	0.04	0.02
	$k_2, \text{ s}$	0.5	0.3
	$D_{GDL}, \text{ cm}^2\text{s}^{-1}$	$13 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$8 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Signal 3: MPL	w_3	0.09	0.01
	$k_3, \text{ s}$	4	1
	$D_{MPL}, \text{ cm}^2\text{s}^{-1}$	$0.06 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$0.02 \cdot 10^{-4}$
$i=112 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$			
Signal 1: Experimental set-up	w_1	0.883	0.005
	$k_1, \text{ s}$	0.0030	5E-5
Signal 2: GDL	w_2	0.05	0.01
	$k_2, \text{ s}$	0.4	0.2
	$D_{GDL}, \text{ cm}^2\text{s}^{-1}$	$16 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$8 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Signal 3: MPL	w_3	0.09	0.01
	$k_3, \text{ s}$	5	1
	$D_{MPL}, \text{ cm}^2\text{s}^{-1}$	$0.05 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$0.01 \cdot 10^{-4}$
$i=42 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$			

Signal 1: Experimental set-up	w_1	0.894	0.006
	k_1, s	0.0031	5E-5
Signal 2: GDL	w_2	0.062	0.01
	k_2, s	0.4	0.1
	D_{GDL}, cm^2s^{-1}	$16 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$4 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Signal 3: MPL	w_3	0.09	0.01
	k_3, s	8	2
	D_{MPL}, cm^2s^{-1}	$0.031 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$0.008 \cdot 10^{-4}$

3. Conclusions

The Current-modulated Hydrogen flow-rate Spectroscopy (CH₂S) has been used to study the transport of hydrogen in the anode of a PEMFC run in passive mode. Three CH₂S signals are observed in CH₂S attributed, respectively, to the experimental set-up time limitation, the hydrogen transport in the GDL, and the hydrogen transport in the MPL. Comparing a conventional-convective PEMFC with a passive PEMFC shows shorter experimental time response for the first one, and larger diffusivities of the GDL and MPL, reflecting lower water saturation in the anode in convective flow cell operation. The effect of the size of the active area of the p-PEMFC has been studied with CH₂S, showing that higher active area promote more accumulation of liquid water in the electrodes and decrease hydrogen diffusivity. Finally, the cell current has little effect on hydrogen diffusivity of the GDL, for values probed here, while increases slightly the diffusivity in the MPL that we explain to a thermal activation effect.

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